

EXPLORING COGRADER TO ENHANCE STUDENT FEEDBACK & ACADEMIC GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

AI-driven grading systems offer significant potential to enhance educational feedback quality, identify student performance patterns, and provide personalised support. These systems have been seen to modernise learning through personalised recommendations and in-depth analysis of student behaviour and performances. This study emphasises a qualitative framework with descriptive analysis to evaluate the benefits of implementing CoGrader, an AI essay grading tool to enhance student feedback and academic growth. The literature review will outline the history of AI-driven grading tools and its subsequent evolution to integrate into human collaborative efforts. The discussion presents the possible strengths and limitations of utilising AI-grading system in a long-term institutional standing, alongside potential recommendations for the tools' improvement. Overall, understanding the role of AI is imperative in the continuous improvement and advancement of education for both students and staff in academia.

Keywords: CoGrader, feedback, artificial intelligence, grading, personalised learning, education

INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been slowly assimilated into important sectors of the population and education is no exception. AI plays multiple roles in education, particularly by modernising learning systems with personalized recommendations and by analysing student performance and behaviour (Lee et al., 2022). Artificial Intelligence grading systems' integration into higher education is a method to combat the labour-intensive process of grading assignments, exams and the expectation of providing constructive feedback to students. However, due to cost and lack of facilities many Malaysian higher education institutions lag behind in implementing AI grading systems.

Before ChatGPT the usage of artificial intelligence in educational contexts are limited, relinquished to spell-checkers or grammar checkers like Grammarly. However, with the release of ChatGPT in November 2022 the capability of artificial intelligence as an administrative assistant has been improved significantly. Multi-tasking is now achievable with the focus of integrating AI into the assessment process, particularly in writing assignments (Alsalem, 2024).

CoGrader follows the same principles. It is an AI essay grading tool developed to acts as an assistant to educators, providing quality feedback on essays and tracking student progress. It emphasises the idea of reducing time to grade in exchange for more quality teaching. It is one of the emerging AI tools that are involved in changing the education landscape and

promoting a growth-oriented environment for students through better feedback loop and detailed comment bank.

According to Norton et al., (2012), the average time spent by educators while a 1,250 words assignment was about 20 minutes; three of the six tutors in the study took less than 15 minutes: four in an hour. The average marking time of twenty student reports worth 2,500 words is extended to 2-3 days, excluding additional class time. The time required for each assignment can vary based on its length and objectives, typically taking between 10 to 15 minutes per assignment. For a sole lecturer handling 123 students, this translates to a daily marking capacity of only 12-15 assignments. Consequently, it is likely for grading to be delayed by up to three weeks while supporting a high number of students, leading to less time for beneficial feedback (Norton, 1990).

This situation can lead to inconsistencies in grading, causing confusion among students who expect clear feedback based on established rubrics. According to Schinske and Tanner (2014), traditional teaching methods often lack a student-centred approach, which hinders students' ability to reflect on their own mistakes. They rely solely on the lecturer for answers, compelling educators to provide detailed feedback to clarify errors.

This study will utilise CoGrader, an AI essay grading tool to assist the lecturers' grading by providing quality feedback on essays. This is done with the emphasise of reducing time to grade in exchange for more quality teaching and improved feedback loop.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The study aims to enhance the feedback and grading process for students using CoGrader. The specific aims are:

1. To explore the predictive analysis of CoGrader to improve student feedback loop with its ability to distinguish grading criteria.
2. To examine CoGrader's algorithmic potential to assist educators as a comment bank for written assignments.
3. To recommend actions university can take to integrate Cograder in improving student support system through human-centric learning and combat overreliance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

HISTORY OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EDUCATION & SERVICE INDUSTRIES

In 1955, a study on artificial intelligence was first proposed by John MsCarthy with the attempt of testing if machines could simulate human facets of principle and knowledge. MsCarthy had worked with theories from Turing (1950) who popularised the possibility of computing machines thinking like humans someday. Even as far back in the 1900s, the research into utilising machines to assist and simulate humans were present, with the AI being correlated to three aspects commonly seen in current day research into artificial intelligence: (1) self, improvement, (2) abstraction, (3) randomness and creativity. MsCarthy believed an 'intelligent' machine was capable of independent improvement. He also states several specific abstract concepts that could be defined through the machine, albeit requiring classification. Finally, in terms of human emotional value, machines could emulate human critical thinking and spontaneity in a controlled and orderly fashion.

Huang and Rust (2018) later adapted the use of AI into the service industry, further classifying MsCarthy's deliberation of AI into four intelligences. While traditionally known as an institution for knowledge, the modernisation of educational practices had led to higher education systems adopting the characteristics of the service industry (Ng & Forbes, 2009). Likened to a customer-centric approach in business, which means putting the customer at the centre of everything you do. The customer, or in the case of education, the students are the focal point for every business and educational decision – from course development to delivery, enrolment, marketing, and growth strategies (Ng & Forbes, 2009).

As such, the four intelligences of AI were distinguished for their abilities to emulate both consistent emotional and analytical skills.

Figure 1. Theoretical framework of the four intelligence and their application to the service industry

Building on John McCarthy's original concept, Figure 1 highlighted the framework for four types of intelligence to help AI learn from experience and adapt on its own. In education, all the listed aspects are necessary for the institution and educators alike to impart successful learning experiences to the students. Thereby the role of AI would be important in the long-term implementation of artificial intelligence into the ever-evolving market of global education.

HUMAN AND AI COLLABORATION

Over the few years, the growth of artificial intelligence has been rapid in the field of industrial and academic research. The topic, however, usually highlights similar limitations, mainly concerns about the replacement of human labour and unoriginality (Owoc et al., 2019). In education, the rising cases of plagiarism and academic misconduct showcases an immediate concern towards students' dwindling literacy skills and overreliance on a machine to complete even simple assignments. As cited in Wilkinson et al (2024), the sophisticated, human-like language generated by ChatGPT raises concerns about academic integrity (Paul et al., 2023). Its ability to create natural-sounding text is so advanced that in one study, academics failed to identify fake scientific abstracts that the AI had produced (Else, 2023). If students misuse ChatGPT to produce assignments, it could severely impede their capacity for critical thought and problem-solving (Fiialka et al., 2023).

Free access to open access AI models like ChatGPT creates an unfair advantage for students in Higher Education Institution (HEI) (Song, 2024). No longer are students' achievement in their assignments a reflection of their learning or confirmation if they have built an adequate knowledge base and skills mastery. Instead, student transcripts are now cast in doubt and suspicion over the intended learning outcomes, making available information on graduates less reliable for policy decisions (Prøitz, 2015).

This led to many research consensuses of hybridising the incorporation of AI into educational systems under human supervision. Even ChatGPT relies heavily on human feedback to generate responses and predict patterns and structures from natural conversations (Atchley et al., 2024). Yet the universality of AI does not deter further studies into more ethical collaboration between human and machine learning.

Most literatures (Grassini, 2023; Halaweh, 2023; Lo, 2023; Sok & Heng, 2023) agree on retaining higher user control while working with artificial intelligence to avoid breaches of academic integrity. The cited literatures have shown ChatGPT can be a helpful productive tool for educator and students in matters of brainstorming or facilitating collaborative work (Grassini, 2023; Halaweh, 2023; Lo, 2023; Sok & Heng, 2023). In fact, the incorporation of AI into classrooms like Google Gemini and ChatGPT offer students immediate feedback and Q&A sessions to enhance their understanding of course materials, leading to improved performance, confidence, and enthusiasm for learning (Imran et.al., 2024).

The ability to facilitate group learning and cater to different characterised student groups makes AI a welcomed collaborator in the educator's repertoire. Artificial intelligence functions as a neutral accessor for students, providing unbiased assessment for each individual student need (Atchley et al., 2024). Such benefits combat the stagnation of relying solely on traditional teaching framework and instead embraces the adoption of AI into streamlining administrative tasks and promote better learning for students geared towards a tech-savvy future.

ARTIFICIAL GRADING SYSTEMS

Automated Essay Scoring (AES) and Automated Writing Evaluation (AWE) systems are artificial intelligence grading systems that utilizes machine learning (ML), and natural language processing (NLP) to assess student-written responses (Semire, 2006). These systems are trained on the responses of human data and relies on using their computational linguistics to analyse and predict patterns in human-written essays. The most common aspect these grading systems recognise to provide feedback are the usage of grammar, structure and language fluency (Shermis & Hamner, 2012; Warschauer & Grimes, 2008).

Early AI relies upon basic statistical models, but modern AI are equipped with deep learning capabilities, which allow the system to interpret linguistic context. (Ramesh & Sanampudi, 2021). In fact, recent companies are utilising deep learning scoring systems (LaFlair & Settles, 2019). Some notable examples include well-established English proficiency test centres like Pearson and Linguaskill have automated their assessments with these AES systems.

Implementation of AES and AWE systems are still volatile within the educational sector (Normann et al., 2023). While largely present in standardised testing centres in learning corporations, the integration of AI into the K-12 and higher education varies due to budgetary constraints or university regulations on AI integrity (Yim & Su, 2025). Construct-response based testing is argued to be more effective in assessing students as it provides more accurate and practical test questions. (Moran, 1987). These written prompts translate to real-life scenarios, thereby facilitating 'natural' progression of knowledge transfer.

With artificial intelligence's capabilities to administrate, revise and promote detailed feedback for both formative and summative assignments, it is clear these systems' benefits cannot be overlooked as a fundamental component for improvements in HEI settings.

METHODOLOGY

CoGrader was utilised to assess the final assessment in several writing-based courses in the span three months. The study involves cohorts of mixed majors: Engineering, Arts, Commerce & Mass Communication. The sample comprised a mixed demographic of students with majorities being Iban, Chinese and Malay ethnicities. Majority of the students were pre-university students while a small cohort were undergraduates. Throughout the three months duration, students' initial marks for the first two assessments were observed. The researchers actively monitored each student' performance through their obtained grades. Other than observation, frequent consultations were another means to improve the lecturers' understanding of each student's learning competencies before the final assignment. These courses focus on contextual literature and critical analysis. Most prominent skills were critical thinking and research skills. In total, we have analysed around 102 student essays (351 students grouped into designated classes) over the span of four different courses.

A qualitative analysis was used for this study to categorise the mark discrepancies between the human and AI accessors. While descriptive statistics were utilised to summarise and support the interpretation of the aggregated grades. This was to maintain the academic integrity of marking, while also to ensure the human lecturers retain majority supervision over the AI-generated comments and alignment to learning outcomes. The syllabi rubrics were validated through strict adherence to Curtin University Bentley Campus materials and moderation, including approval under the Malaysian Qualifications Framework (MQA). Collected assignments were deposited into CoGrader and graded with fixed prompts for each designated class.

Table 1. Total number of students for designated courses with CoGrader

Student Groupings and Total Number of Students per Course		
Course	Student Groupings	Total Number of Students
CMFP0023 Critical Thinking	56	264
CMFP0022 Writing and Research Skills	14	55
ASIA1003 Peoples, Culture, and Borneo	3	13
COMS1003 Culture to Cultures (<i>individual</i>)	n/a	19
Total	73	351

Note. COMS1003 Culture to Cultures was conducted individually without groupings.

The final assessment utilised in the data collecting stage of this research consisted of students structuring analytical reports, reflections and critical reviews on pre-determined topics. Majority of the assignments were group work due to large cohorts, specifically for CMFP0023 Critical Thinking, ASIA1003 Peoples, Culture, and Borneo, and CMFP0022 Writing and Research Skills. These courses had students grouped into 3-6 students per team. These cohorts were then split into 25-30 student classrooms, thus the existences of different groupings with a designated lecturer. Smaller classrooms like COMS1003 Culture to Cultures had assessments done individually and had 18 students in one classroom. All assignments were similar in rubrics, but the AI visibly struggles with more creative-aligned marking criterions that were present in COMS1003 Culture to Cultures.

Quantitative data is derived from CoGrader and lecturers' grades on student performance. The data is then transferred into a form in Microsoft Word. The form is standardised with criteri-

ons to moderate the differences between lecturer(human)graded and AI-graded assignments. Each assignment is moderated in an individual form, listing down the students or groups that were part of the assessment.

Course Name and Code: ASIA1002 Peoples and Cultures of Borneo

Assesment 1:Research Exercise

Student 1

AI Grade: 24/30

AI Comment:

You demonstrate a good understanding of the impact of modernization on the Lun Bawang community in Sarawak. Your analysis is clear and supported by relevant examples, such as the transition from animistic beliefs to Christianity and the effects of urbanization on traditional practices. However, the essay could benefit from a deeper exploration of the complexities and nuances of cultural change, as well as a broader comparison with other indigenous communities in the region.

Lecturer Grade: 21/30

Lecturer Comment:

Student needed to do a more detailed analysis on the subject matter and not do a surface level treatment on the chosen topic matter.

Mark differences: 3 marks

Mark difference range:

High/Low/Neutral

Noted Limitations:

Tended to be lenient even after setting changed to be more stricter.

Assessor solutions or recommendation:

The leniency and the acceptance of the uploaded rubric at face value, makes it necessary for lecturers to still go through student work to check for nuances or misunderstanding that might occur during the marking process.

Figure 2. Example of the Grading Qualitative Data Form

Figure 2 illustrates the form's structure with the purpose of comparing and analysing the reflection of both the human and AI feedback for a particular student. Each assignment was moderated individually up to three times and assessed with viable recommendations and comments from the supervising lecturer, which were also taken into consideration as qualitative data on the AI grading system's accuracy.

Upon receiving the assignments, the AI would provide an initial evaluation of the student's work based off the assigned rubrics and prompt. Once the marks were generated, lecturers can customise the marks and include additional feedback that were relevant to the student. This ensured the integrity of the grading process, as the AI-generated marks were then compared to the final moderated grades assigned by the lecturers.

Following this comparison, it was important to emphasize that the role of AI in this process is supportive rather than substitutive. The AI provided valuable assistance in grading, allowing lecturers to focus on delivering quality feedback and engaging more deeply with their teaching practices.

At the end of semester, the grades were analysed and the qualitative conclusion determine whether CoGrader could provide feedback that aligns with the educators' marking criteria. The analytics generated from this study would be then used to improve grading rubrics or potentially help in identifying feasible action through the alignment of students' grades found in the assessments.

The comments generated by the machine would also be used as a form of comment bank, which were checked for accuracy three times for the final assignment per course. Comments

generated by CoGrader is monitored to be consistent and because of the uploaded marking rubrics, the decision of awarding marks was done objectively.

RESULTS

Utilising descriptive analysis, data collection was conducted for 102 student essays. The data were systematically categorised and interpreted for their mark discrepancies between the AI and human assessors. The discrepancies were divided into: None, Neutral, Low and High discrepancies. These levels were distinguished by their consistent gap between marks. None denotes perfect agreement with 0 discrepancies. Neutral was 1-3 marks, but still consistent. Low was 4-7 marks while High level indicates major discrepancies if the grades between human and AI assessors were 8 marks and above.

The aggregated grades were then assigned into the corresponding discrepancy level after the moderation between the lecturers' and Cograder's marks were recorded in the data form. To further align the discrepancies between the marks and the feedback, the frequencies (number of groups or students) were converted into percentage as means to interpret the overall differences between human and AI collaboration.

Figure 3. Group mark discrepancies for CMFP0023 Critical Thinking and CMFP0022 Writing and Research Skills

For CMFP0023 Critical Thinking (CT), CoGrader showed higher similarity in grades between lecturer and AI unlike more specific rubrics for CMFP0022 Writing and Research Skills (WRS). Figure 3's data shows perfect agreement between the AI and lecturer is rare, occurring for only 9% of groups. Most groups fall between neutral agreement and a low-level discrepancy of 24%.

The differences for CT were minimal with only 1-2 marks among the criteria while WRS showed large discrepancies of up to 10 marks. The most common outcome by far is a Neutral discrepancy, which applies to 63% of all groups. This indicates that the AI and lecturer might not grade exact same scores, but their assessments of the students' written abilities were still consistent.

The WRS assessment required two rescoring with the prompt "be stricter" to align with lecturer's grading. While CT had multiple instances where the AI graded the students with the exact marks as the lecturer, pointing out similar weaknesses of said assignment. However, High discrepancy is uncommon. Major disagreements were isolated to only 4% of groups. Overall, this suggests the two grading methods will inevitably reach a similar evaluation.

Figure 4. Group discrepancies within ASIA1002 Peoples and Cultures of Borneo

For Peoples and Cultures of Borneo assignments, there's a notable lack of perfect agreement. As noted from Figure 4, 69% majority of group marks between human and AI assessors occurred within the Neutral discrepancy. Furthermore, there are no major discrepancies with 31% of groups falling in the Low discrepancy level. All scores were determined to be within moderate ranges. However, there was a difference of perfect alignment between the group and individual assessments of these two courses.

Figure 5. Individual discrepancies within COMS1003 Culture to Culture

Figure 5 shows COMS1003 Culture to Culture and ASIA1002 Peoples and Cultures of Borneo shared similar results. There were no major disagreements, however the key difference was the possibility of perfect agreement, with 6% exact match present. The common outcome for 78% majority were Neutral discrepancy while the remaining 16% of students were in Low discrepancy.

This distinction emphasises that even with closely aligned outcomes for both assessment types, evaluation of collaborative work makes identical scores less frequent. The scoring was consistently highlighted by minor to moderate differences, suggesting a small but systemic variance applied to two assessors while grading.

The key findings show minimal discrepancies between cohorts, indicating that combining human and AI grading ensured consistent results and improved efficiency. This indicates that the grading criteria for both assignment types were adequately clear and objective for both the human lecturer and the AI to apply without any drastic divergences in assessment.

Ultimately, the results highlighted the capabilities of CoGrader's competency in aligning its marking algorithm to learning outcomes with minimal divergence. Despite requiring human accessors to design specific criteria templates to ensure better predictive grading from the AI, this shows CoGrader's innate deep-learning model is adequate to improve the feedback loop while maintaining academic integrity in marking.

DISCUSSION

Throughout the study, it's clear that Cograder can reduce the workload and grading time of educators as emphasised by the website (CoGrader, nd). The tailored and detailed qualitative feedback for each individual essay is a highlight for both researchers and educators. Overall, most educator acknowledge the AI-software can only be as good as the user, prompting prior training knowledge (Alsaalem, 2024). However, there are some strengths and limitations to the AI- grading tool's that requires strict human supervision and prompting.

STRENGTHS

One of the strengths of CoGrader are the comments. CoGrader generates personalised comment for each student assessment which details specific solutions and constructive critiques. The comments provided have significantly assisted the lecturers in improving their own feedback for each individual student's work.

From the usage of English learning, CoGrader proves highly effective for progression checks and consultations. Its granular feedback provides lecturers with early visibility into student misunderstandings and common flaws before formal marking. This allows educators to track ongoing progress, anticipate recurring issues, and validate whether corrections are implemented between draft submissions. While the AI's highly specific reports occasionally requires mark adjustments, specifically nuanced interpretations of context or creativity, its automated metrics shows strong alignment with human grading criteria across quantitative rubrics. This consistency reduces lecturers' initial workload, freeing them to focus on higher-order feedback.

The tool's detailed diagnostics enables lecturers to personalise student guidance and refine instructional strategies. By categorising errors and competency gaps, Cograder identifies systemic misconceptions in research methodologies or theories that informs targeted lesson adjustments and individualised improvement plans.

An example is the comment assigned to an assignment. The assignment has a perfect agreement of 24 marks from both human and AI accessors.

CoGrader comment:

Your critique demonstrates a solid grasp of the article's main arguments and identifies some logical fallacies. However, to achieve a higher standard, you need to be more critical in evaluating the evidence, scrutinize the author's tone and potential bias, and connect the article's arguments to broader societal impacts. Your summary should be more concise and clearly separated from your analysis, and your organization and clarity would benefit from improved transitions and simpler language. Focus on these areas to strengthen your analytical writing.

The AI's summary of the critique highlights the lack of critical review of the evidence but praises the students' understanding of the main arguments and language, even if slightly verbose.

Lecturer Comment:

Good identification of the logical fallacies and has a good grasp of the article's premise. However, the critique is mostly a summary of the article and has little critical review into the author's potential bias and overall analysis of broader societal impacts millennials have on future generation.

Both comments share the main bulk of feedback necessary for the students' improvement and shows CoGrader's comments can be used as a reliable assistant for additional and helpful feedback on assignments.

Ultimately, CoGrader' usage as a grading tool extends beyond the usual functions. It can be used as generic comment bank; however, it is still necessary to filter through the generated comments which will be discussed in the Limitations below.

LIMITATIONS

For ASIA1002 Peoples and Cultures of Borneo and COMS1003 Culture to Cultures, CoGrader is unable to function properly when evaluating creative works. The two courses have some elements of creative work like poster making, poetry, short story compositions and other examples of media text. When deposited into CoGrader, the AI reverts to the rubrics that was uploaded. Marks were generated, but it failed to view and understand nuances in creative works of the students.

In another example of the potential weakness of CoGrader, the AI repeated itself several times during a Case Study assessment trial in COMS1003 Culture to Cultures. CoGrader "hallucinated" the results by producing comments that are not related to the rubric. Other than that, it had also failed in some instances of grading the creative works.

CoGrader could not detect individual students' contribution in group work, this was also the case for the Group Presentation assessment of ASIA1002 Peoples and Cultures of Borneo. The similar limitation is shared with the other courses, pertaining to more specific rubric requirements which are present in CMFP0022 Writing & Research Skills as well.

The machine also tends to be lenient even after the "Be Stricter" choice had been selected. This was also the conclusion made by Mizumoto and Eguchi (2023, as cited in Li et al, 2024). In this instance, the issue could be attributed to the inexperience of the lecturer to fine-tune the settings of CoGrader. Perhaps through online self-learning or seminars, this can be remedied to a certain extent.

Despite the limitations, the results from the study highlighted CoGrader as a communal comment bank to improve the current student support systems for quicker, more efficient feedback and contributing to current integration efforts for artificial intelligence. However, it should be noted that educators should not rely on the sole judgement of the AI regarding assessment marking, instead utilising CoGrader's algorithmic analysis in planning personalised lesson plans for each classes' needs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Our research has found that educators remain at the forefront of the learning cycle and should be prioritised in the academic development of students, especially for the transitioning period from secondary to tertiary education. To mitigate the limitations and reliance of utilizing grading tools like CoGrader, we recommend the implementation of a human-centred learning and teaching framework (HCLTF) as proposed in Kong and Yang (2024)'s study. Albeit designed to prepare K-12 learners and teachers, the framework is still viable in training academics in higher education regarding ethical usages of generative AI for instructional teaching and materials. This can be the supplemented programme to train educators in the usage of AI-powered educational technologies. Students would benefit from the programme with more individualised feedback with an emphasis on collaborative learning environments.

Figure 6. Kong's HCLTF with incorporation of GenAI in K-12 settings

The frame aims to unify three domains of pedagogical teaching and the rising change of tech-mediated learning. With the strict adherence to human-centric monitoring, the framework would attempt to build a cohesive and dynamic learning environment that supports SRL and prepares students for the demands of the 21st century (Kong & Yang, 2024). This human-centred approach ensures that the essential human aspects of learning and teaching, such as empathy, ethical considerations, and social interactions, are maintained and strengthened (Kong & Yang, 2024).

The end goal is to test the feasibility of implementing CoGrader as a facilitation tool for marking. Such is with the intention of reducing the time spent on marking assignments and allow for more individualised feedback sessions that effectively supports student's improvement. The AI's capability of generating analytics for overall class performances with minimal variation in grades between the human accessor gives valuable insight into the personalisation for student's academic growth. The AI-grading tool has shown promise in helping educators understand learning curves for varying groups of learners.

This aligns with the cyclic improvement model of action research, which is often conducted in educational settings to provide sustainable improvement and resolve real-world issues in student learning (Riel, 2019). Every cycle would allow the researcher to investigate any apparent variables without being confined to only one process. For example, our study has revised and

evaluated the identification and description of the problem multiple times throughout the research. Even when the main issue is surmised as students' shallow evaluation in both evidence-based analysis and critical evaluation of claims for critical thinking assignments, we have found that the problem runs deeper with more social matters like student motivation, insufficient language proficiencies and the current emergence of more present neurodivergent students.

The process allows educators to refine objectives and reflect on the academic needs of the students in this current technological era as the cycle can be repeated severally, focusing on the same or on a different emerging variable/problem altogether (Lassonde & Galman, 2009). According to Oranga and Gisore (2023), guided instruction enables students to develop systematic problem-solving skills by investigating solutions and implementing appropriate strategies, with action plans designed to be age-appropriate and address students' immediate needs.

The goal should be to enhance the learning experience for students while supporting educators in their vital roles. CoGrader has shown to facilitate a practical journey forward through methodologies similar to action research. With the incorporation of Kong's framework, it is plausible CoGrader can be integral tool in institution to build progressive academic growth for students, educators and researchers.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, CoGrader has shown potential to not just assist lecturers in grading, but to retain the academic standards required in promoting students' educational growth. The significant finding of this study indicates a collaborative human-AI framework is the most effective model for enhancing pedagogical outcomes. The framework can be used to improve the quality assurance of existing HEI standards and contribute to MQA's goal for academic excellence and lifelong learning.

Academics might contemplate familiarising themselves with the technology as a grading aid, to support a human-in-the-loop grading process, providing supplementary resources and time, moderating and refining individual feedback, to increase consistency and quality. While having limitation in grading creative endeavours, AI grading systems like CoGrader is still capable of contributing to the feedback loop while maintaining the ethical marking standards that can only be fulfilled by human educators.

The study outlines an actionable model for implementing CoGrader within institutional grading systems. By utilising CoGrader's analysis of competencies in writing assignments, educators can deliver more personalized, timely, and substantive feedback to each student. Therefore, the adoption of such a collaborative system is an important step for any academic institution dedicated to advancing educational quality and equity in a modern learning landscape.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this research.

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